

MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS IN LESSONS OF CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Annotation: *This article discusses modern interactive methods used in teaching children's literature and how to attract children's attention to the lesson.*

Keywords: *demonstration, children's literature, analysis, video lessons, interactive methods.*

Introduction: The age, knowledge and level of education of the students are taken into account when performing demonstration in literature classes. Each exhibition has its own security and usage requirements. Full compliance with these requirements should be in the constant attention of every teacher. Because the prepared exhibition must be hygienically and psychologically suitable for the student.

In addition, it is required to know the specific principles of correct timing and adherence to the use of each prepared exhibition, as well as to use it in accordance with the purpose of the lesson. In the process of preparing each exhibition, specific tools are used, and during training, they must be used correctly, efficiently and safely. The quality of the prepared exhibits, their suitability for the intended purposes, their convenience and their correct use have a positive effect on increasing the effectiveness of training. It is an integral part of methodical activity to organize that each teacher prepares educational materials from certain types of exhibitions for practical use in the course of training. In this regard, teachers are recommended to prepare a lesson plan for conducting a lesson on a topic of their choice using the most appropriate visual aids and conduct open lessons based on it.

Fiction reflects existence through vivid scenes and images. By its very nature, literature itself is a visual representation of existence. But other types of art: film, television, music, visual arts can also help in literature lessons. They serve as an

additional source of information for literature lessons, allow the formation and development of aesthetic feelings in students, and also help the images created by the writer to be more carefully imprinted in the student's mind. Currently, various film cameras, televisions, tape recorders are available in almost every school and every home. Due to this, the range of visual aids has expanded.

It is worth noting that the use of visualization in the classroom and in extracurricular activities differ significantly in their nature and have different goals. In circle work, extracurricular activities, the teacher can, for example, set the task of expanding the students' imagination about a certain type of art or introducing the students to a visual art, a piece of music, a television film or a movie. This will definitely have a positive effect on students' mastery of literary works. Although the interaction of literature with other forms of art is not the same, students' experiences of film, theater, music, and visual arts have a significant impact on their literary development.

In the lesson, visualization can be used only to the extent that it can help students master the work. Otherwise, it may come to the fore and the main topic may take a back seat. The main task of visualization in literature classes is to help students to understand the literary work, helping to fully imagine the writer's creativity, creating an additional opportunity to acquire literary-theoretical concepts, to ensure the development of students' speech, in a word, to help solve all the tasks facing the literature teacher.

This feature can have different properties in each specific case. When using visualization, it is possible to conditionally talk about the passive or active participation of the student in the lessons. If visual aids do not have a positive effect on student activity, it is better not to use them.

If we are talking about the literature of the past or the works related to foreign life, the importance of visibility increases even more. Because the student has a brighter and clearer knowledge and imagination about the events and events that he has dimly imagined or has no idea at all. In this case, the explanation of the teacher is lacking, this place is filled by demonstration. Visualization is also present in the teacher's commentary. Although in such cases passivity is felt in the student, but this does not reduce the role of visibility at all. But it is important that the student reaches the level of active communication, conversation, and active thinking by means of visualization. Visibility is such only if it helps to reveal certain aspects of the literary process, event or image. It is also effective to involve students in making their own visual aids in increasing and activating students' knowledge. In particular, it is possible to involve the

students themselves in defining poetic weights, distinguishing literary types and genres. It is also useful in strengthening certain knowledge in students.

Conclusion: *By way of conclusion, the tasks of visualization in the process of teaching children's literature can be extremely diverse. Currently, its types are extremely diverse, and each of them can be related to visual, auditory, synthetic forms of visual aids.*

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